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THE HISTORY OF TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH WRITING SKILLS IN UZBEKISTAN (POST-SOVIET STATE). PEDAGOGICAL DIAGNOSTIC APPROACH

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ANNOTATION

This article explores the development of English writing instruction in Uzbekistan throughout three significant time periods: the Soviet era, the 1991–2012 transitional period, and the contemporary era. English writing training was strict during the Soviet era, emphasizing formulaic patterns, grammar, and translation while placing little value on originality or critical thought. Although issues like out-of-date curricula and unequal resource distribution remained, there was a slow shift toward communicative approaches during the post-independence years (1991–2012). Globalization and legislative changes have made English writing teaching more dynamic in the current day, with a focus on technology integration, critical thinking, and practical skills. The article emphasizes how different regulations and standards in each era influenced instructional strategies, mirroring more general shifts in societal demands and educational priorities. By exploring these differences, the article underscores the transformative journey of English writing teaching in Uzbekistan.

Key words: pedagogical diagnostics, Foreign Language Teaching (FLT), English Writing Skills, Uzbekistan Education System, Post-Soviet Language Policy, Presidential Decree PD-1875, Educational Reform, Language Instruction Methods, Writing Pedagogy, Pre-Independence FLT, Modern English Teaching Standards, CEFR Implementation, Language Policy Transformation.

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O'ZBEKISTONDA INGLIZ TILINI YOZISH KO'NIKMALARINI O'RGATISH VA O'RGANISH TARIXI (POSTSOVET DAVLATI). PEDAGOGIK DIAGNOSTIKA YONDASHUVI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda ingliz tilini yozish ta'limining rivojlanishi uchta muhim davr: Sovet davri, 1991–2012-yillar o'tish davri va hozirgi davrni o'rganadi. Sovet davrida ingliz tilida yozishni o'rgatish qat'iy bo'lib, formulalar, grammatika va tarjimaga urg'u berib, o'ziga xoslik yoki tanqidiy fikrga unchalik ahamiyat bermagan. Eskirgan o'quv dasturlari va resurslarning teng taqsimlanmaganligi kabi muammolar saqlanib qolgan bo'lsa-da, mustaqillikdan keyingi yillarda (1991–2012) kommunikativ yondashuvlarga sekin siljish kuzatildi. Globallashuv va qonunchilikdagi o'zgarishlar texnologiya integratsiyasi, tanqidiy fikrlash va amaliy ko'nikmalarga e'tibor qaratgan

holda, bugungi kunda ingliz tilini yozishni o'qitishni yanada dinamik qildi. Maqolada har bir davrdagi turli qoidalar va standartlar ta'lim strategiyalariga qanday ta'sir qilgani, jamiyat talablari va ta'lim ustuvorliklarida umumiy o'zgarishlarni aks ettirganligi ta'kidlangan. Ushbu farqlarni o'rganish orqali maqola O'zbekistonda ingliz tilini o'qitishning o'zgaruvchan sayohatini tasvirlab beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: pedagogik diagnostika, chet tillarini o'qitish (FLT), ingliz tilini yozish ko'nikmalari, O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimi, postsovet tili siyosati, Prezidentning PD-1875 farmoni, ta'lim islohoti, til o'qitish metodikasi, yozish pedagogikasi, mustaqillikdan oldingi FLT, zamonaviy ingliz tilini o'qitish standartlari, ingliz tilini o'qitish standarti.

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ИСТОРИЯ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ И ИЗУЧЕНИЯ НАВЫКОВ ПИСЬМА НА АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ (ПОСТСОВЕТСКОЕ ГОСУДАРСТВО). ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЙ ДИАГНОСТИЧЕСКИЙ ПОДХОД

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматривается развитие обучения письму на английском языке в Узбекистане на протяжении трех важных периодов времени: советская эпоха, переходный период 1991–2012 годов и современная эпоха. В советское время обучение письму на английском языке было строгим: упор делался на шаблонные модели, грамматику и перевод, а оригинальность или критическое мышление ценились мало. Хотя такие проблемы, как устаревшие учебные программы и неравное распределение ресурсов, сохранялись, в годы после обретения независимости (1991–2012) наблюдался медленный сдвиг в сторону коммуникативных подходов. Глобализация и законодательные изменения сделали преподавание письма на английском языке более динамичным в наши дни, уделяя особое внимание интеграции технологий, критическому мышлению и практическим навыкам. В статье подчеркивается, как различные правила и стандарты в каждую эпоху влияли на стратегии обучения, отражая более общие сдвиги в общественных требованиях и образовательных приоритетах. Рассматривая эти различия, статья подчеркивает трансформационный путь преподавания письма на английском языке в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: педагогическая диагностика, преподавание иностранных языков (FLT), навыки письма на английском языке, система образования Узбекистана, постсоветская языковая политика, Указ Президента УП-1875, образовательная реформа, методы обучения языку, педагогика письма, FLT до обретения независимости, современные стандарты преподавания английского языка, внедрение CEFR, трансформация языковой политики.

Introduction.

Three different eras have seen substantial changes in Uzbekistan's teaching and learning of English: the Soviet era, the years after independence (1991–2012), and the post–2012 period following the implementation of Presidential Decree PD-1875. Changes in methodology, educational objectives, and the larger sociopolitical environment are reflected in each time. In line with international educational standards such as the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR), the recent focus on pedagogical diagnostics has become a crucial strategy for enhancing writing instruction (Rustamov, 2025).

Period 1: The Soviet Era (Pre-1991) - A Foundation of Grammar and Translation

English language instruction was significantly impacted by ideological factors and a centralized curriculum throughout the Soviet era. The most common pedagogical approach was the grammatical-Translation Method, which placed a strong emphasis on rote memorization of grammatical rules, vocabulary learning through lists, and translation exercises between English and

Russian (and rarely Uzbek, although Russian was the major language of instruction). Throughout the Soviet era, English language teaching was significantly impacted by the grammar-translation technique and centralized policies (Yakovleva, 1987.). The two fundamental components of writing training were rote memorization and mechanical translation exercises. The primary objective was to enhance reading comprehension and translation abilities rather than communication skills. Academic composition and creative writing were largely disregarded, and formative evaluation and individualized learning were not given any thought.

Curriculum and Resources: The central Ministry of Education prescribed texts for the highly standardized curriculum. The emphasis was on developing a passive understanding of the language and mastering grammatical structures.

Writing Activities: Writing assignments were mostly restricted to regulated composition, such as translating texts, creating phrases according to predetermined patterns, or filling in the spaces. Authentic communication and creative writing were mostly lacking.

Teacher Role: Grammatical rules and error correction were the main responsibilities of teachers, who were viewed as knowledge providers. The classroom environment was frequently formal and teacher-centered, and there was little opportunity for student involvement.

Evaluation: Grammar correctness was the main focus of the evaluation, with little attention paid to content, structure, or communicative efficacy.

Period 2: The Transitional Years (1991-2012) - Experimentation and the Rise of Communicative Language Teaching.

Uzbekistan realized it needed to upgrade and internationalize its educational system after gaining independence in 1991. During this time, language instruction began to gradually move toward communicative methods. However, a lack of updated instructional materials, insufficient teacher training, and a lack of resources made the changeover sluggish (Kosimov & To'lqinboyeva, 2024).

During this time, English writing instruction continued to struggle with antiquated approaches while attempting to promote the use of language in real-world contexts. Assessment techniques prioritized linguistic precision above fluency or coherence, and writing assignments continued to be grammar-focused. In the classroom, teacher-centered methods predominated, and diagnostic methods were rarely used to meet the needs of specific students (Jalolov J., G.Tojjeva, 2012).

Yet, in the early years of independence, English writing instruction remained heavily influenced by Soviet-era methods. But as Uzbekistan became more open to the outside world, exposure to foreign teaching resources and methods started to change how classes were conducted. A major change was brought about by the advent of communicative language teaching (CLT), which prioritized meaningful communication over memorization. English became widely used as a language for business and international communication. This time frame was distinguished by:

Curriculum Reform: The strict Soviet curriculum started to relax and place more of a focus on improving communication skills. Teachers and students were exposed to innovative pedagogical ideas through the increasing introduction of textbooks from Western publishers.

Adoption of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT): The concepts of CLT, which place a strong emphasis on real tasks, meaningful engagement, and student-centered learning, started to have an impact on instructional strategies. Instructors began implementing exercises that pushed pupils to communicate in English in everyday situations.

Enhanced Resource Availability: Students can now engage with genuine English materials thanks to the wider accessibility of English resources such as books, journals, and the internet.

Teacher Training Programmes: A number of teacher training programs were developed so as to equip teachers with skills necessary for the implementation of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT). This initiative however did not always go well and juxtaposed teaching remained due to insufficient resources, training, and low self-esteem of teachers.

Writing Exercises: More free and creative writing activities included letters, emails, short reports, and simple essays. Yet, there was never a shortage of emphasis on grammatical accuracy, causing students to struggle with creativity and fluency.

Period 3: The Era of Reforms Matched with CEFR (Post-Presidential Decree PD-1875, December, 10, 2012) – Quality Focused.

An introduction to law on December 10, 2012 under Presidential Decree PD-1875 fundamentally changed the teaching of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan, marking the beginning of new and transformative reforms. These shifts aimed at improving the quality and matching it with the international pedagogical standard the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) integrated into almost every sector of ELT. Out of some major:

Curriculum Overhaul Based on the CEFR: The national curriculum was completely updated to conform to the CEFR, defining learning objectives for every level of competency (A1-C2). This gave pupils a well-defined, globally accepted framework for language learning, guaranteeing that they advanced methodically through predetermined competency levels.

Adoption of CEFR-Aligned Textbooks: To choose textbooks that satisfied CEFR requirements, a thorough evaluation procedure was used, with a focus on student-centered activities, authentic materials, and communicative ability. This supported successful language acquisition and made sure that the teaching resources matched the updated curriculum.

Support for language learning in early childhood: Elementary schools had programs that allowed students to learn a foreign language from an early age. This was intended to give students a solid grounding in language learning at an early age.

Encouraging CEFR/IELTS: Since 2016, Uzbekistan has required CEFR/IELTS B2 certificates for university entrance exams. This law encourages potential students and teachers to improve their English language skills in speaking, writing, reading, and listening. It has played a major role in improving English language education.

Better Teacher Training: English teachers in Uzbekistan have been certified at the C1 level of the CEFR/IELTS, which has improved teachers' language skills and work in the classroom. The policy encourages teachers to develop higher levels of competence in listening, speaking, reading, and writing, to teach high-level courses, and to use new pedagogical methods.

New ways to test students: Schools are now replacing old-style grammar tests with tests that check how well students can use language in real-life situations. These new tests include tasks such as writing essays, giving speeches, and acting out conversations.

The Role of Pedagogical Diagnostics in Teaching Writing Today.

In Uzbekistan, pedagogical diagnostics has emerged as a key instrument for enhancing English writing education. This method uses continuous formative evaluations to systematically identify learners' strengths and weaknesses. It enables educators to adapt their lessons to each student's needs, improving writing skills and promoting differentiated instruction (Rustamov, 2025).

Pedagogical diagnostics are used in teaching writing in the following ways:

Initial Diagnostics: Evaluating students' foundational writing skills to guide instructional planning and curriculum development (Ferris, 2014). Using ongoing, focused feedback to monitor student development and fix particular writing deficiencies is known as formative assessment (Wiliam, 2011).

Individualized Learning Plans: Creating tailored educational programs to meet the various needs of students (Godwin-Jones, 2020). Using diagnostic methods allows teachers to provide more individualized training, which improves student results and supports the CEFR's focus on communicative ability (Rustamov, 2024).

In conclusion

The changes in English writing instruction in Uzbekistan reflect broader shifts in education and politics. We've seen big steps forward from the rigid, grammar-centered methods of Soviet times to today's communicative diagnostic-based approaches. Various government and Presidential Decrees have a major impact on writing education pushing for global standards and up-to-date teaching methods. As Uzbekistan becomes more connected to the world strong English writing skills are growing in importance for its people. To ensure Uzbek students gain the English writing abilities they need to thrive in the 21st century and beyond, it'll be essential to blend teaching diagnostics well with ongoing teacher training and access to diverse resources.

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